

ACTIVITIES TO ACTIVATE AND MAINTAIN A COMMUNICATIVE CLASSROOM

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Abstract: Student-centered instruction is a shared goal in English as a second or foreign language settings that embrace communicative language teaching (CLT) principles. Student-centered classrooms create opportunities for learners to have consistent and meaningful interactions – two-way exchanges of ideas – using their second language (L2). Such interactions promote (L2) development, as peers provide modified input and speakers are pushed to produce language that their partners understand. As the popularity of student-centered classrooms has grown, knowledge-based objectives (testing for grammar and vocabulary knowledge) have been overtaken by more-communicative learning objectives. Beyond memorizing grammar or vocabulary for drills or exams, students must show that they can use real-life language to perform speaking and writing activities, often in small groups.

Key words: This article will first discuss CLT principles and important criteria for communicative activities in the classroom.

CLT teachers choose classroom activities based on what they believe is going to be most effective for students developing communicative abilities in the target language (TL). Oral activities are popular among CLT teachers, as opposed to grammar drills or reading and writing activities, because they include active conversation and creative, unpredicted responses from students. Activities vary based on the level of language class they are being used in the TL. The six activities listed and explained below are commonly used in CLT classrooms.

Role-play is an oral activity usually done in pairs, whose main goal is to develop students' communicative abilities in a certain setting.

Example:

1. The instructor sets the scene: where is the conversation taking place? (E.g., in a café, in a park, etc.)
2. The instructor defines the goal of the student's conversation. (E.g., the speaker is asking for directions, the speaker is ordering coffee, the speaker is talking about a movie they recently saw, etc.)
3. The students converse in pairs for a designated amount of time.

Interview is an oral activity done in pairs, whose main goal is to develop students' interpersonal skills in the TL.

Example:

1. The instructor gives each student the same set of questions to ask a partner.
2. Students take turns asking and answering the questions in pairs.

This activity, since it is highly structured, allows for the instructor to more closely monitor students' responses. It can zone in on one specific aspect of grammar or vocabulary, while still being a primarily communicative activity and giving the students communicative benefits. This is an activity that should be used primarily in the lower levels of language classes, because it will be most beneficial to lower-level speakers.

Group work is a collaborative activity whose purpose is to foster communication in the TL, in a larger group setting.

Example:

1. Students are assigned a specific role within the group of no more than six people.
2. Students are assigned a specific role within the group.(E.g., member A, member B, etc.)
3. The instructor gives each group the same task to complete.
4. Each member of the group takes a designated amount of time to work on the part of the task to which they are assigned.
5. The members of the group discuss the information they have found, with each other and put it all together to complete the task.

Students can feel overwhelmed in language classes, but this activity can take away from that feeling. Students are asked to focus on one piece of information only, which increases their comprehension of that information.

Information gap is a collaborative activity, whose purpose is for students to effectively obtain information that was previously unknown to them, in the TL.

Example:

1. The class is paired up. One partner in each pair is Partner A, and the other is Partner B.
2. All the students that are Partner A are given a sheet of paper with a time-table on it. The time-table is filled in half-way, but some of the boxes are empty.
3. All the students that are Partner B are given a sheet of paper with a time-table on it. The boxes that are empty on Partner A's time-table are filled in on Partner B's time-table, but they are filled in on Partner A's.

4. The partners must work together to ask about and supply each other with the information they are both missing, to complete each other's time-tables.

Completing information gap activities improves students' abilities to communicate about unknown information in the TL.

Opinion sharing is a content based activity, whose purpose is to engage students' conversational skills, while talking about something they care about.

Example:

1. The instructor introduces a topic and asks students to contemplate their opinions about it.(E.g., dating, school dress codes, global warming)

2. The students talk in pairs or small groups, debating their opinions on the topic.

Opinion sharing is a great way to get more introverted students to open up and share their opinions. If a student has a strong opinion about a certain topic, then they will speak up and share.

Scavenger hunt is a mingling activity that promotes open interaction between students.

Example:

1. The instructor gives students a sheet with instructions on it.(e.g. Find someone who has a birthday in the same month as yours.)

2. Students go around the classroom asking and answering questions about each other.

3. The students wish to find all of the answers they need to complete the scavenger hunt.

In doing this activity, students have the opportunity to speak with a number of classmates, while still being in a low-pressure situation, and talking to only one person at a time. After learning more about each other, and getting to share about themselves, students will feel more comfortable talking and sharing during other communicative activities.

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